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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF LOVASTATIN
TRANSDERMAL PATCHES****Dr.T.Mangilal*, Mrs.T.Sowmya, Lokam Neeraja, Suppa Anusha, Mohd. Mudassir,
T. Ruthika Goud, M. swetha**Smt.Sarojini Ramulamma College of Pharmacy, Seshadrinagar, Mahabubnagar-509001,
Telangana, India.**Abstract:**

The skin can be used as the site for drug administration for continuous transdermal drug infusion into the systemic circulation. For the continuous diffusion/penetration of the drugs through the intact skin surface membrane-moderated systems, matrix dispersion type systems, adhesive diffusion-controlled systems and micro reservoir systems have been developed.

In the present work, an attempt has been made to develop a matrix-type transdermal therapeutic system comprising of Lovastatin with different ratios of polymers Eudragit L100 and Ethyl Cellulose using solvent evaporation techniques. The physicochemical compatibility of the drug and the polymers was studied by FTIR. The results obtained showed no physical-chemical incompatibility between the drug and the polymers. F8 formulation has been selected as the optimized formulation among all the other formulations because of the highest concentration of penetrating enhancer with the highest concentration of ethyl cellulose. The in vitro drug diffusion studies from the formulation were found to be released (99.36 ± 2.04 %) up to 12 hours. All the evaluation parameters obtained from the best formulation were found to be satisfactory.

Keywords: Lovastatin, Permeation Enhancer, and Transdermal drug delivery.

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INTRODUCTION:

Controlled drug delivery system

Treatments of acute and chronic diseases have been accomplished by delivery of drugs to patients using various pharmaceutical dosage forms. These dosage forms are known to provide a prompt release of drug. But recently several technical advancements have been done and resulted in new techniques for drug delivery. These techniques are capable of controlling the rate of drug release.

The term controlled release has a meaning that goes beyond scope of sustained release. The release of drug ingredients from a controlled release drug delivery advances at a rate profile that is not only predictable kinetically, but also reproducible from one unit to other¹. The difference between sustained release and controlled release is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Comparative graphs of conventional, sustained- and controlled release delivery systems.

The classification of controlled drug delivery can be given as follows.

1. Rate-preprogrammed drug delivery systems
2. Activation-modulated drug delivery systems
3. Feedback-regulated drug delivery systems
4. Site-targeting drug delivery systems

Out of these classes first class contains new drug delivery systems as trans dermal delivery, intra uterine delivery, ocular inserts, and sub dermal implants. The trans dermal drug delivery has advantage to deliver medicines via skin to systemic circulation at a predetermined rate and maintain therapeutic concentration for prolong period of time.

Transdermal drug delivery

The idea of delivering drugs through skin is old, as the use is reported back in 16th century B.C. Today the transdermal drug delivery is well accepted for delivering drug to systemic circulation.

Until recently, the use of transdermal patches for pharmaceuticals has been limited because only a few

drugs have proven effective delivered through the skin typically cardiac drugs such as nitroglycerin and hormones such as estrogen.

Definition: Transdermal therapeutic systems are defined as self-contained discrete dosage forms which, when applied to the intact skin, deliver the drug(s), through the skin, at controlled rate to the systemic circulation.

The first Transdermal drug delivery (TDD) system, Transderm-Scop developed in 1980, contained the drug Scopolamine for treatment of motion sickness. The Transdermal device is a membrane-moderated system. The membrane in this system is a microporous polypropylene film. The drug reservoir is a solution of the drug in a mixture of mineral oil and polyisobutylene. This study release is maintained over a one-day period.

Non-medicated patch markets include thermal and cold patches, nutrient patches, skin care patches (a category that consists of two major sub-categories — therapeutic and cosmetic), aroma patches, and weight loss patches, and patches that measure sunlight exposure. Transdermal drug delivery has many advantages over conventional drug delivery and can be discussed as follows.

Advantages^{2, 3, 4, 5}

1. They can avoid gastrointestinal drug absorption difficulties caused by gastrointestinal pH, enzymatic activity, and drug interactions with food, drink, and other orally administered drugs.
2. They can substitute for oral administration of medication when that route is unsuitable, as with vomiting and diarrhea.
3. They avoid the first-pass effect, that is, the initial pass of drug substance through the systemic and portal circulation following gastrointestinal absorption, possibly avoiding the deactivation by digestive and liver enzymes.
4. They are noninvasive, avoiding the inconvenience of parenteral therapy.
5. They provide extended therapy with a single application, improving compliance over other dosage forms requiring more frequent dose administration.
6. The activity of a drugs having short half-life is extended through the reservoir of drug in the therapeutic delivery system and its controlled release.
7. Drug therapy may be terminated rapidly by removal of the application from the surface of the skin.
8. They are easily and rapidly identified in emergencies (e.g., unresponsive, unconscious, or

comatose patient) because of their physical presence, features, and identifying markings.

9. They are used for drugs with narrow therapeutic window. At the same time transdermal drug delivery has few disadvantages that are limiting the use of transdermal delivery.

Disadvantages^{3, 4, 6}

1. Only relatively potent drugs are suitable candidates for transdermal delivery because of the natural limits of drug entry imposed by the skin's impermeability.
2. Some patients develop contact dermatitis at the site of application from one or more of the system components, necessitating discontinuation.
3. The delivery system cannot be used for drugs requiring high blood levels.
4. The use of transdermal delivery may be uneconomic. For better understanding of transdermal drug delivery, the structure of skin should be briefly discussed along with penetration through skin and permeation pathways.

1.3. Structure of skin

An average adult skin has a surface area of approximately 2 square meters and receives about one third of the blood circulating through the body. It is one of the most readily accessible organs of the human body with a thickness of only a few millimeters (2.97+/-0.28 mm). Its major roles are to regulate body temperature, protect tissues from infection, prevent fluid loss, and cushion internal structures^{7, 8}

Figure 2. Structure of skin

The skin is a multilayered organ composed of many histological layers. It is generally described in terms of three major tissue layers.^{6, 9, 10.}

- **The epidermis** – thin protective outer layer.
- **The dermis** – the tough elastic second layer.
- **The hypodermis** – layer of fatty and connective tissue.

The Epidermis

The outer (epidermal) layer of the skin is composed of stratified squamous epithelial cells. The multilayered envelope of the epidermis varies in thickness, depending on cell size and then number of cells and then number of cell layers, ranging from about 0.8mm on the palms and the soles down to 0.66mm on the eyelids. Cells which provide epithelial tissue differ from those of all other organs provide epithelial tissue differ from those of all other organs in that as they change in an ordered fashion from metabolically active and dividing cells to dense, dead, keratinized protein.

Stratum germinativum (basal layer):

The basal cells are nucleated, columnar, and about 6 microns wide, with their long axis at right angles to the dermoepidermal junction; they connect by cytoplasmic intercellular bridges. Mitosis of the basal cells constantly renews the epidermis and this proliferation in healthy skin balances the loss of dead horny cells from the skin surface. The epidermis thus remains constant in thickness. Below the basal cell layer lies the complex dermoepidermal junction, which constitutes an anatomic functional unit. The junction serves three functions of dermal-epidermal adherence, mechanical support for the epidermis, and control of the passage of cells and some large molecules across the junction.

Stratum spinosum (prickle cell layer)

As the cells produced by the basal layer move outward, they alter morphologically and histochemically. The cells flatten and their nuclei shrink. These polygonal cells are called as prickle cells because they interconnect by fine prickles.

Stratum granulosum (granular layer)

As the Keratinocytes approach the surface, they manufacture basic staining particles, the keratohyalin granules. It was suggested that these granules represent an early form of keratin 3, 4. The term transitional zone is convenient region between living cells and dead keratin.

Stratum lucidum

In the palms and the soles an anatomically distinct, poorly staining hyaline zone forms a thin, translucent

layer immediately above layer immediately above the granular layer. This region is the stratum lucidum.

Stratum corneum (horny layer)

As the final stage of differentiation, epidermal cells construct the most the superficial layer of the epidermis, the stratum corneum. On general body areas the membrane provides 10-15 layers of much flattened, keratinized dead cells (corneocytes). Ultimately these cells are sloughed off through desquamation. A keratinocyte's journey from basal layer to horny layer takes about 14 days. The cell travels through the layers of stratum corneum for another 14 days before it is finally shed. So the normal turnover rate of the epidermis is atleast 28 days. The stratum corneum plays a crucial role in controlling the percutaneous absorption of drug molecules.

The barrier nature of stratum corneum depends critically on its unique constituents; 75-80 % is protein, 5-15 % is lipid with 5-10 % unidentified on a dry weight basis. The protein is located primarily within the keratinocytes and is predominantly alpha-keratin (around 70 %) with some beta-keratin (approximately 10 %) and a proteinaceous cell enveloping (around 5 %). Enzymes and other proteins account for approximately 15% of the protein component. The cell envelop protein is highly insoluble and is very resistant to chemical attack. This outer keratinocytes protein has a key role in structuring and ordering the intercellular lipid lamella of the stratum corneum; the keratinocytes is bound to a lipid envelop through glutamate moieties of the protein envelop. The lipid envelop thus provides an anchor to the keratinocytes and links the proteinaceous domains of the keratinocytes to the intercellular lipid domains. Human stratum corneum is a unique mixture of lipids and, for most permeates; the continuous multiply bilayered lipid component of the stratum corneum is key component in regulating drug flux through the tissue. It is clear that the lipid content of the stratum corneum varies between individuals and with body site, but major components of the domain include ceramides, fatty acids, cholesterol, and cholesterol sulfate and sterol/waxesters.

Figure 2 The structural relationship between stratum corneum, viable epidermis, and the capillary network at the dermoepidermal junction.

The Dermis

The dermis (cornium) consists essentially of a matrix of connective tissue woven from fibrous proteins which embed in an amorphous ground substance on muco polysaccharides providing about 20 % of the mass. Blood vessels, nerves, and lymphatics cross this matrix and skin appendages (eccrine sweat glands, apocrine glands and pilo sebaceous units) penetrate it. In man, the dermis divides into a superficial, thin papillary layer which forms a negative image of the rigid lower surface of the epidermis, and a thick underlying reticular layer which merges with the fat-containing subcutaneous tissue.

The dermis needs a rich blood supply which regulates temperature and pressure, delivers nutrients to the skin and removes waste products, mobilizes defense forces, and contributes to skin color. The blood supply reaches to within 0.2 mm of the skin surface, So that it readily absorbs and systemically dilutes most chemicals which penetrate past the stratum corneum and the viable epidermis. The vascular surface available for the viable epidermis. The vascular surface available for the exchange of materials between local tissues and the blood is enormous. Of particular relevance to biopharmaceutical studies is the fact that this generous blood volume usually functions as a "sink" with respect to the diffusing molecules which reach it during the process of percutaneous absorption. This sink condition ensures that the penetrate concentration in the dermis remains near and therefore the concentration gradient across the epidermis is maximal.

The Hypodermis

This is a sheet of fat-containing areolar tissue known as superficial fascia, attaching the dermis to the underlying structure.

Skin Appendages

The epidermis and dermis support several appendages: The exocrine, apocrine and sebaceous glands, the hair follicles and the nails. Of these, hair follicles and sweat ducts can act as diffusion shunts, i.e. relatively easy pathways for diffusion through the rate-limiting stratum corneum.

Figure 3 Transepidermal (A) and trans appendageal route of transport into the skin. The transappendageal route (B) includes diffusion via the hair follicle and the sweat gland.

Exocrine Sweat glands: Exocrine sweat glands develop over the skin surface but not over mucous membranes. The gland density varies greatly with skin site; for example, the thighs possess about 120 glands per square centimeter and the soles of the feet have about 620 per square centimeter. The composition and the quantity of the sweat varies greatly with subject, time, environmental conditions, exertion and skin site.

Apocrine Sweat Glands

Apocrine sweat glands are epidermal appendages which develop throughout the skin of the embryo as part of the pilosebaceous follicle. Most of the glands subsequently disappear so that the characteristic adult distribution is in the axilla, the perianal region and the areola of the breasts.

Hair follicles

Hair follicles developed over the entire skin surface except the palms the soles, the red portion of the lips

and the parts of the sex organs. The average fractional surface area of the openings is about 0.1%. Hair contains “hard” keratin, which differs from the “soft” keratin of desquamating tissues in its high sulfur content.

Sebaceous Glands

Sebaceous glands are largest and most numerous on the back. The palms and soles are usually free of them. The flask like sebaceous glands form ducts which usually open into the neck of the hair follicle. Sebum is complex mixture of lipids i.e. glycerides, free fatty acids, wax esters, squalene, cholesterol, esters. Several functions have been attributed to sebum, such as controlling water loss, and protecting the skin from fungal and bacterial infection.

Skin Pathways For Transdermal Drug Delivery Systems

When drugs are applied on the skin surface, penetration into and through the skin can occur via various routes.

Drugs penetrate either via the stratum corneum (Trans epidermal) or via the appendages (transappendageal) (Figure 3 and 4). During penetration through the stratum corneum, two possible routes can be distinguished¹¹.

- i) Penetration alternating through the corneocytes and the lipid lamellae (transcellular route) and
- ii) Penetration along the tortuous pathway along the lipid lamellae (intercellular route).

Generally it is accepted that the predominant route of penetration through the stratum corneum is the intercellular route. This is mainly caused by the densely cross-linked cornified envelope coating the keratinocytes. However trans cellular transport for small hydrophilic molecules such as water cannot completely be excluded the appendage route or shunt route includes either the duct of the eccrine sweat glands or the follicular duct. The content of the eccrine sweat glands is mainly hydrophilic, while the content of the follicular duct is lipophilic. This is mainly due to the sebum excreted into the opening of the follicular duct. It is generally accepted that due to its large surface area, passive skin permeation mainly occurs through intact stratum corneum.

Figure 4 Simplified Representation of skin showing routes of penetration:

Permeation Enhancers⁹

These are the compounds, which promote skin permeability by altering the behavior of skin as barrier to the flux of a desired penetrant. The flux, J , of drugs across the skin can be written as:

$$J = D \frac{dc}{dx} \text{ ----- (1)}$$

Where,

D is the diffusion coefficient and is a function of the size, shape and flexibility of

The diffusing molecule as well as the membrane resistance;

C is the concentration of the diffusing species;

x is the spatial coordinate.

Thus enhancement of flux across membranes depends on the considerations of:

- Thermodynamics (lattice energies, distribution coefficients)
- Molecular size and shape
- Reducing the energy required to make a molecular hole in the membrane

Permeation enhancers are hypothesized to affect one or more of the layers to achieve skin penetration enhancement. A large number of compounds have been investigated for their ability to enhance stratum corneum permeability. These conveniently classified under the following main headings:

Solvents

These compounds increase penetration possibly by

- 1). Swelling the polar pathways in the skin.
- 2). Fluidization of lipids.

Examples include water alcohols-methanol and ethanol; alkyl methyl Sulphoxides-dimethyl

Sulphoxide, alkyl homologs of methyl Sulphoxide, dimethyl acetamide and dimethyl formamide; pyrrolidones-2-pyrrolidone; laurocapram (Azone), miscellaneous solvents-propylene glycol, glycerol, silicone fluids, isopropyl palmitate.

Surfactants:

These compounds are proposed to enhance polar pathway transport, especially of hydrophilic drugs.

The ability of a surfactant to alter penetration is a function of the head group and the hydrocarbon chain length. These compounds are skin irritants, therefore, a balance between penetration enhancement and irritation have to be considered. Anionic surfactants can penetrate and interact strongly with the skin. Once these surfactants have penetrated the skin, they can induce large alterations. Cationic surfactants are reportedly more irritant than the anionic surfactants and they have not been widely studied as skin permeation enhancers. Of the three major classes of surfactants, the non-ionics have long been recognized as those with the least potential for irritation and have been widely studied. Examples of commonly used surfactants are:

Anionic Surfactants

Dioctylsulphosuccinate, Sodiumlauryl sulphate, Decyldecylmethyl Sulphoxide etc.

Nonionic Surfactants: Pluronic F127, Pluronic F68, etc.

Bile Salts : Sodium taurocholate, Sodium deoxycholate, Sodium tauroglycocholate.

Miscellaneous chemicals: These include urea, a hydrating and keratolytic agent; N, N-dimethyl-m-toluamide; Calcium thioglycolate; Anticholinergic agents.

Some potential permeation enhancers have recently been described but the available data on their effectiveness are sparse. These include eucalyptol, di-o-methyl-beta-cyclodextrin and soyabean casein.

c) Other excipients:

Adhesives:

The fastening of all Transdermal devices to the skin has so far been done by using a pressure sensitive adhesive. The pressure sensitive adhesive can be positioned on the face of the device or in the back of the device and extending peripherally.

Both adhesive systems should fulfill the following criteria.

- Should not irritate or sensitize the skin or cause an imbalance in the normal skin flora during its contact time with the skin.
- Should adhere to the skin aggressively during the dosing interval without its position being disturbed by activities such as bathing, exercise etc.
- Should be easily removed.

- Should not leave an unwashable residue on the skin.
- Should have excellent (intimate) contact with the skin at macroscopic and microscopic level.

Backing membrane

Backing membranes are flexible and they provide a good bond to the drug reservoir, prevent drug from leaving the dosage form through the top, and accept printing. It is impermeable and protects the product during use on the skin e.g. metallic plastic laminate, plastic backing with absorbent pad and occlusive base plate a (aluminum foil), adhesive foam pad (flexible polyurethane) with occlusive base plate (aluminum foil disc) etc.

Technologies for developing transdermal drug delivery systems¹

The technologies can be classified in four basic approaches.

A. Polymer membrane partition-controlled TDD systems:

In this type of systems, the drug reservoir is sandwiched between a drug impermeable backing laminate and a rate controlling polymeric membrane. (Figure 4)

Figure 4 Cross-sectional view of polymer membrane permeation controlled TDD systems

The drug is allowed to permeate only through the rate controlling membrane. The drug solids are homogeneously dispersed in a solid polymer matrix, suspended in an unleachable, viscous liquid medium e.g. silicone fluid, to form a paste like suspension, or dissolved in a releasable solvent e.g. alkyl alcohol, to form a clear drug solution. The rate controlling membrane can be either a microporous or a non porous polymeric membrane e.g. ethylene-vinyl acetate copolymer, with specific drug permeability. On the external surface of the polymeric membrane a thin layer of drug compatible, hypoallergenic pressure sensitive adhesive polymer e.g. silicone adhesive, may be applied to provide intimate contact of TDD system with the skin surface.

Varying the composition of drug reservoir formulation and the permeability coefficient and

thickness of rate controlling membrane can alter the drug release rate.

E.g. Some FDA approved systems – Transderm-Nitro for angina pectoris, Transderm-Scop for motion sickness, Catapres-TTS system for hypertension.

The intrinsic rate of drug release from this type of TDD system is defined by

$$\frac{dQ}{dt} = \left(\frac{K_m/r K_a/m D_a D_m}{K_m/r D_m h_a + K_a/m D_a h_m} \right) C_R$$

Where, C_R is drug concentration in reservoir compartment;

K_m / r the partition coefficient for the interfacial partitioning of drug from there serivoir to the membrane

K_a / m the partition coefficient for the interfacial partitioning of drug from membrane to adhesive

D_a diffusion coefficient in rate controlling membrane

D_m diffusion coefficient in adhesive layer

h_a thickness of rate controlling membrane

h_m thickness of adhesive layer

Enhancement of Transdermal Permeation

If the drugs under study have not got great abilities to cross the skin, ways must be found to modify the diffusional barrier or to increase drug permeation by another way. Passive permeation across the stratum corneum is especially difficult to compounds, which are hydrophilic ($\log P_{oct} < 1$), very lipophilic ($\log P_{oct} > 3$), of high molecular weight (M.Wt. > 400 g/mol) or charged.

Advances in Transdermal Permeation Enhancement

To achieve and to maintain a plasma drug concentration above the minimum therapeutic drug level, the barrier properties of the skin must be overcome before the effective transdermal controlled delivery of drugs can be successfully accomplished, the following approaches have been shown to be potentially promising for accomplishing the goals of reducing skin barrier properties and enhancing the transdermal permeation of drugs.

Generally, methods to enhance transdermal drug permeation can be grouped into two categories: Chemical methods and Physical methods.

a) Physical approach

- Stripping of stratum corneum
- Hydration of stratum corneum

- Phonophoresis or Sonophoresis
- Iontophoresis
- Electroporation
- Jet Injectors
- Microneedles

b) Chemical Approach

- Co-administration of skin permeation enhancer
- Delipidization of skin permeation enhancer
- Synthesis of lipophilic analogs

c) Biochemical approach

- Synthesis of bioconvertible prodrugs
- Co-administration of skin metabolism inhibitors

- **Table 1. Techniques based on active transport for enhancing TDDS¹⁴**

a) Physical Methods^{11,12}

These methods have been tested to create effective transdermal drug delivery.

Microneedles: Micro fabricated needles approximately 150 µm long were able to increase the permeability of the human skin. These arrays of micro needles create conduits across stratum corneum potentially allowing the transport of drug molecules. This technology provides hope for an effective transdermal system for the delivery of macromolecules.

Macroflux: Macroflux technology is another novel TDDS to deliver biopharmaceutical drugs in a controlled reproducible manner that optimizes bioavailability and efficacy without significant discomfort for the patient. The system incorporates a titanium micro projection array that creates superficial pathway through the skin barrier layer to allow transportation of therapeutic proteins.

Phonophoresis or Sonophoresis: Enhancement of migration of drug molecules through the skin by ultrasonic energy. These acoustic waves used in the frequency range from 20 KHz to 20MHz are known to interact with tissue through several physical phenomena like refraction, transmission, absorption, scattering etc. Drugs like Immunosuppressant's, Steroids, Anti-inflammatory analgesics, Local anaesthetics, Proteins (insulin), Antiviral (interferons), and Antibodies etc. are tested.

Iontophoresis and Electroporation: Iontophoresis involves use of electrical current or voltage to deliver charged or uncharged molecules into the skin. Electroporation involves the creation of transient aqueous pathways in the lipid bilayer membrane by the application of a short electric field pulse. Two main pulse protocols have been employed to promote transport; intermittent application of short high-voltage pulses (about 1ms and 100V across the skin) and a few applications of long medium-voltage pulses (about 100ms and > 30V across the skin).

Electro-Osmosis: If a charged porous membrane is subjected to a voltage difference, a bulk fluid or volume flow, called electro-osmosis occurs without concentration gradients, suggesting that this flow is not diffusion. This bulk flow by electro-osmosis was found to be of the order of micro liters per hour per square centimeter of hairless mouse skin. The electro-osmotic flow occurs from anode to cathode, thus enhancing the flux of positively charged drugs and making it possible to deliver neutral drugs.

Jet injectors: Jet injectors use brute force to deliver therapeutic moieties through the skin. There are wide ranges of delivery devices like gene-guns, which propel DNA coated gold beads through the skin by helium.

Transfersomes: The most promising transdermal drug carrier is the recently developed and patented Transfersomes which penetrates the skin barrier along the transcutaneous moisture gradient. This leads the carriers through the virtual pores between the cells in the organ without affecting its biological and general barrier properties. Lipid based suspensions, such as liposomes and niosomes, have been proposed as low risk drug carriers. Transfersomes carriers can create a highly concentrated drug depot in the systemic circulation.

Magnetophoresis: Magnetophoresis is a novel approach in enhancing drug delivery across biological barriers. Benzoic acid, a diamagnetic substance, was selected as a drug candidate. The influence of magnetic field strength on diffusion flux was determined and was found to increase with increasing applied strength.

Laser Radiation: This method involves direct and controlled exposure of a laser beam to the skin which

results in the ablation of the stratum corneum without significantly damaging the underlying epidermis. Removal of stratum corneum using this method has been shown to enhance the delivery of lipophilic and hydrophilic drugs.

b) Chemical enhancers and prodrugs In this method various chemicals are used to enhance the permeation across the skin which acts as a tough barrier. Ex DMSO, menthol, limonene, etc.¹⁶

Mechanism

The enhancement in absorption of oil soluble drugs is apparently due to the partial leaching of the epidermal lipids by the chemical enhancers, resulting in the improvement of the skin conditions for wetting and for transepidermal and transfollicular penetration. The miscibility and solution properties of the enhancers used could be responsible for the enhanced transdermal permeation of water-soluble drugs. Some of them alter the composition of the cell content while others affect the cohesiveness between cells and composition of intercellular material or have a direct effect on cell membrane. The composition of intercellular lipids undergoes a solid-lipid phase transition at 40°C. It is possible that some penetration enhancers act to disrupt the structure of intercellular lipids and lower the phase transition temperature, thereby increasing the permeability of skin to more polar compounds. To increase the rate of transfer of lipophilic compounds, it is necessary to modify the partitioning characteristics at the stratum corneum viable tissue interface. This may be possible by combining a penetration enhancer with a co-solvent. Some agents can establish a reservoir in stratum corneum, which may facilitate diffusion of drug, when penetrating the epidermis, may carry drug through, by acting as a solvent. Many of these agents may act by a combination of various effects on the skin while others may be involved in a direct chemical insult on the skin. When the specified lipid film, made up of sebaceous secretion, desquamated cells, sweats and other components, the percutaneous absorption is enhanced slightly. When lipids are removed from the skin as by means of prolonged exposure to polar solvents, however, considerably enhanced absorption of applied materials. It is quite likely that lipid solvents must damage the lipid portion of the membrane before much change in passage through the skin can take place. The existence of a depot or reservoir for topically applied drugs within the stratum corneum was postulated by Malkinson and Furgoson.

Prodrugs have been used to improve the drug delivery across the skin, because of a lot of nonspecific esterases and other enzymatic activities are present in the epidermis.

Classification of penetration enhancers:¹⁷

- i. Terpenes (essential oils): E.g. Nerodilol, menthol, 1 8 cineol, limonene, carvone etc.
- ii. Pyrrolidones: E.g. N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), azoneetc.
- iii. Fatty acids and esters: E.g. Oleic acid, linoleic acid, lauric acid, capric acid etc.
- iv. Sulphoxides and similar compounds: E.g. Dimethyl Sulphoxide (DMSO), N, Ndimethylformamide.
- v. Alcohols, Glycols, and Glycerides: E.g. Ethanol, Propylene glycol, Octyl alcohol, etc.
- vi. Miscellaneous enhancers: E.g. Phospholipids, Cyclodextrins, Amino acid derivatives, Enzymes etc.

Desirable characteristics of penetration enhancers

These are the some of the desirable characteristics of penetration enhancers:

- The material should be pharmacologically inert and should possess no action of itself at receptor sites in the skin or in the body generally.
- The material should not be toxic, irritating or allergenic.
- On application, the onset of penetration enhancing action should be immediate; the duration of the effect should be predictable and suitable.
- The enhancer should be chemically and physically compatible with a wide range of drugs and pharmaceutical adjuvant.
- The substance should be an excellent solvent for drugs.
- The material should spread well on the skin and be cosmetically acceptable.
- The substance should be inexpensive, odorless, tasteless and colorless.

No single penetration enhancer can possess all the required properties. However, many enhancers exhibit many of these attributes and they have been tested in clinical or research laboratories. Pharmaceutical scientists have made great efforts in transdermal permeation studies using various enhancers for several drug moieties.

Terpenes as permeation enhancers

Terpenes and terpenoids are usually the constituents of volatile oil. Their chemical structure consists of repeated isoprene units (C_5H_8) and as classified according to the number of isoprene units: monoterpenes have two isoprene units (C_{10}), sesquiterpenes have three (C_{15}) and diterpenes have four (C_{20}). Terpenes may also be entropy changes associated with the lipid related transitions, particularly T2 the first major lipid transition.

Fatty acids and esters as penetration enhancers (oleic acid)

A large number of fatty acids and their esters have been used as permeation enhancers. A general trend has been seen that unsaturated fatty acids are more effective in enhancing percutaneous absorption of drugs than their saturated counter part. Oleic acid is obtained from edible fats and fixed oils. It is often obtained as a byproduct in the production of stearic acid. It consists of cis-9-octadecenoic acid and is a colourless to pale yellow, oily liquid. It is practically insoluble in water, but miscible with alcohol. It gradually absorbs oxygen and darkens when exposed to air.

Mechanism of action of fatty acids and esters

Fatty acids and esters assist the percutaneous absorption of both water soluble and oil-soluble

drugs. The enhancement in the absorption of oil-soluble drugs is apparently due to the partial leaching of the skin conditions for wetting and for transdermal and Tran's follicular penetration.

General clinical considerations in the use of TDDS³

The patient should be advised of the following general guidelines. The patient should be advised of the importance of using the recommended site and rotating location within the site. Rotating locations is important to allow the skin to regain its normal permeability and to prevent skin irritation.

1. TDDSs should be applied to clean, dry skin relatively free of hair and not oily, inflamed, irritated, broken, or callused. Wet or moist skin can accelerate drug permeation beyond onset time. Oily skin can impair the adhesion of patch. If hair is present at the site, it should be carefully cut, not wet shaved, nor should a depilatory agent be used, since later can remove stratum corneum and affect the rate and extent of drug permeation.

2. Use of skin lotion should be avoided at the application site, because lotions affect the hydration of skin and can alter partition coefficient of drug.

3. Cutting should not physically alter TDDSs, since this destroys integrity of the system.

4. The protecting backing should be removed with care not to touch fingertips. The TDDS should be pressed firmly against skin site with the heel of hand for about 10 seconds.

Table 2 Examples of marketed transdermal drug delivery system

Sl. No	Therapeutic agent	Marketed name (company)
1.	Clonidine	Catapres-TTS (Boehringer Ingelheim)
2.	Estradiol	Vivelle (Novartis)
3.	Fentanyl	Duragesic (Janssen)
4.	Nicotine	Prosstep (Lederle)
5.	Testosterone	Testoderm (Alza)
6.	Nicotine	Habitrol (Novartis Consumer)
7.	Nicotine	Nicoderm CQ (Smithkline Beecham consumer)
8.	Nitroglycerine	Transderm-Nitro (Novartis consumer)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initially the drug was tested by UV to know their significant absorption maximum which can be used for the diffusion study of the drug.

Analysis of Drug

A. Determination of absorption maximum

The absorption maximum (λ_{max}) of Lovastatin was found to be 254 nm by scanning between 200-600 nm by using UV-VISIBLE Spectrophotometer; it is useful for the further estimation of drug in pure form and dosage form.

B. Construction of calibration curve

Table 4 Standard graph of Lovastatin

Sl. No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance (at254 nm)
1	0	0
2	5	0.145
3	10	0.302
4	15	0.477
5	20	0.623
6	25	0.766

Figure 5 Standard calibration curve of Lovastatin

Preformulation study

Totally, ten formulations were trials (F1 to F6) were done with the aim to achieve the successful matrix type Lovastatin transdermal patches. The blend trials prepared for the drug was evaluated for various physical parameters and content uniformity of drug by UV-VISIBLE spectroscopy.

A. Colour, Odour, taste and appearance

Table 5 Organoleptic results of drug

Sl. No	Parameter	Lovastatin
1	Color	White
2	Odor	Odorless
3	Taste	Bitter
4	Appearance	A white powder

B. Determination of Melting point

Table 9. Results of Melting point tests of drug

Sl. No	Drug	Reported melting point
1	Lovastatin	174.5 ⁰ C

C. Determination of solubility

Table 6 Solubility profile

Sl. No	Solvent	Drug solubility(mg/ml)
1	Distilled water	42.03
2	pH 7.4 phosphate buffer	72.3

Evaluation of Patch

The formulations F1 to F6 were varying in thickness when compared to other formulations which is due to the variation in the polymer concentration. Which shows the increase in polymer concentration increases the thickness of patch. For all other formulations it was found to be in between 0.030 ± 0.002 to 0.036 ± 0.003 mm.

Folding endurance from formulations F1 to F6 was found to be in between 75 ± 0.86 to 87 ± 1.13 which can withstand the folding of the skin.

All formulations showed % drug content from 98.22 ± 1.04 to 99.98 ± 0.98 .

% Moisture absorbed and % Moisture loss of all the formulations were showed from 2.03 ± 0.01 to 2.54 ± 0.01 and 1.05 ± 0.02 to 1.63 ± 0.02 .

Formulation of lovastatin patches F1 to F6**F5 F6**

F5**Table 8 Evaluation of transdermal patches-I**

Formulation Code	Thickness (mm)	Folding endurance	Flatness (%)	Appearance	% Drug Content
F1	0.033± 0.001	78± 0.96	99.7	Transparent	98.3 ± 1.57
F2	0.030± 0.002	76± 1.05	100	Transparent	99.85 ± 0.86
F3	0.036± 0.001	80± 1.25	100	Transparent	99.52 ± 0.95
F4	0.034± 0.003	79± 1.10	99.9	Transparent	98.22 ± 1.04
F5	0.035± 0.001	81± 1.08	100	Transparent	99.68 ± 1.14
F6	0.031± 0.002	78± 1.10	100	Transparent	99.51 ± 1.14

Table 9 Evaluation of transdermal patches-II

Formulation code	% Moisture absorbed	% Moisture lost
F1	2.43 ± 0.02	1.34 ± 0.03
F2	2.12 ± 0.01	1.11 ± 0.01
F3	2.32 ± 0.01	1.14 ± 0.02
F4	2.27 ± 0.02	1.23 ± 0.01
F5	2.15 ± 0.03	1.05 ± 0.02
F6	2.03 ± 0.01	1.12 ± 0.03

A. *In vitro* diffusion study:

All the formulation *in vitro* diffusion study was carried out by using Franz type diffusion cell under specific condition such as temp maintained at 37±0.5°C. The diffusion was carried out for 12 hr and 5 ml sample was withdrawn at an interval of every 1 hr.

Table 10 *In Vitro* Drug Permeation Of Lovastatin Containing Different Concentrations Of Eudragit L 100 + Ethyl Cellulose And 10 % DMSO

Time (hr)	F1	F2	F3
0	0	0	0
1	25.14 ± 1.05	19.22 ± 1.02	13.27 ± 1.14
2	37.08 ± 2.05	27.09 ± 0.98	21.55 ± 2.04
3	49.22 ± 1.55	36.34 ± 1.23	28.23 ± 1.56
4	60.07 ± 2.14	47.17 ± 1.87	35.47 ± 1.07
5	77.19 ± 1.62	59.21 ± 2.11	42.19 ± 1.31
6	85.17 ± 1.01	64.63 ± 1.13	50.28 ± 1.28
7	99.18 ± 2.18	76.28 ± 1.86	59.37 ± 1.74
8	99.29 ± 1.15	87.29 ± 1.05	66.46 ± 2.13
9	-	99.32 ± 2.11	73.28 ± 2.21
10	-	-	84.37 ± 1.48
11	-	-	91.21 ± 1.36
12	-	-	99.36 ± 2.04

Figure 11 Cumulative % drug permeation of Lovastatin patch

(F1, F2 and F3)

The formulations F1 to F3 were prepared by different ratios of Eudragit L 100: Ethyl cellulose (1:1, 1:2 and 1:3), the drug release or drug permeation from the patch was dependence on the concentration of polymer and permeation enhancer in the matrix. The 1:1 and 20 % DMSO (F1) concentrations was showed maximum drug release 99.18 ± 2.18 within 7 hours. The 1:2 and 20 % DMSO (F5) concentrations was showed maximum drug released at 9 hours

99.32 ± 2.11 %. The 1:3 and 20 % (F3) concentrations of polymer and permeation enhancer was showed maximum drug release 99.36 ± 2.04 at desired time period (12 hours). Hence in that 3 formulation F3 formulations showed total drug release at desired time period.

Table 12 *In vitro* drug permeation of Lovastatin containing different concentrations of Eudragit L 100 and ethyl cellulose and 20 % of DMSO

Time (hr)	F4	F5	F6
0	0	0	0
1	16.47 ± 1.21	12.15 ± 1.62	10.28 ± 1.14
2	25.03 ± 1.35	20.06 ± 2.11	19.46 ± 1.34
3	36.18 ± 2.04	29.52 ± 1.84	27.52 ± 2.28
4	43.24 ± 1.83	38.37 ± 2.01	35.47 ± 1.42
5	52.35 ± 2.11	47.46 ± 1.47	41.61 ± 1.61
6	61.63 ± 1.46	56.08 ± 1.16	48.07 ± 2.11
7	74.34 ± 1.28	64.31 ± 2.14	54.36 ± 2.14
8	85.25 ± 1.51	71.49 ± 1.55	59.13 ± 1.76
9	99.38 ± 2.14	79.30 ± 1.39	65.23 ± 1.23
10	-	86.21 ± 2.03	70.31 ± 1.41
11	-	92.55 ± 1.47	76.43 ± 1.53
12	-	99.87 ± 1.26	84.37 ± 1.47

Figure 6 Cumulative % drug permeation of Lovastatin patch (F4, F5 and F6)

The formulations F4 to F6 were prepared by different ratios of Eudragit L 100 and ethyl cellulose (1:1, 1:2 and 1:3) and 20% permeation enhancer, the drug release or drug permeation from the patch was dependent on the concentration of polymer and permeation enhancer in the matrix. The 1:1 (F4)

concentration of polymer was showed maximum drug release 99.38 ± 2.14 within 9 hours. The 1:2 (F5) concentration of polymer showed maximum drug released at 12 hours 99.87 ± 1.26 %. The 1:3 (F6) concentration of polymer was showed maximum

drug release after 12 hours. Hence this was not considered.

Among all 6 formulations, F5 formulation showed good drug permeation from the patch.

Among all in vitro evaluation parameters F5 formulation passed all evaluation parameters.

CONCLUSION:

Finally, it is concluded that Transdermal patch of Lovastatin, a lipid lowering agent can be efficiently and successfully formulated by employing solvent evaporation method.

Evaluation parameters like thickness, folding Endurance, indicated good mechanical resistance of the patch for all the formulations.

Percentage moisture content and drug content uniformity were found to be within the approved range (Indian Pharmacopoeial Standards) for all the formulations.

The *in-vitro* diffusion study showed 99.87 ± 1.26 % of drug release at the end of 12 hrs from the formulation (F8).

Further detailed investigation is required to establish bioavailability studies and efficacy including pre-clinical studies and clinical studies of this novel transdermal patch.

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